

GIBLING'S CORRECTIONS. PART II

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Group parachor values for the groups $(C)CH_2Cl$, $(C)_2CHCl$ and $(C)_3CCl$ have been evaluated from the parachor values of aliphatic monochlorides. The differences between the parachor values of $(C)CH_2Cl$, $(C)_2CHCl$ and $(C)_3CCl$ are similar to those found by Gibling in case of $(C)CH_3$, $(C)_2CH_2$ and $(C)_3CH$ respectively. The results are discussed as regards the interference correction for $C-C-Cl$.

In continuation of the previous communications (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 471, 799) the interference correction for $C-C-Cl$ is derived from the parachor values of aliphatic monochlorides in the present paper. Gibling (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 299, 306; 1944, 384) obtained the interference correction values for $C-C-C$, $C-C-()$ and $C-C-S$ as 2.2, 2.6 and 2.7 respectively and assumed the interference correction for $C-C-N$ as 2.4 (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 149). Although Gibling (*ibid.* 1943, 151) has calculated the group parachor values for the groups $(C)CH_2Cl$, $(C)CH_2Br$ and $(C)CH_2I$, no mention has been made by him as regards the interference corrections for $C-C-X$, where X may be a halogen atom. In the present paper, group parachor values for the groups $(C)CH_2Cl$, $(C)_2CHCl$ and $(C)_3CCl$ have been derived from the parachor values of ethyl, isopropyl and *tert.*-butyl chloride respectively.

The mean of the observed parachor values of ethyl chloride (Mme. Hennant-Roland and Lek, *Bull. Soc. chim. Belg.*, 1931, 40, 177; Vogel, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 636) may be taken as 151.7. From this the group parachor value for the group $(C)CH_2Cl$ may be calculated as 96.3.

Similarly the mean observed parachor value of isopropyl chloride (Vogel, *loc. cit.*) may be taken as 191.6. From this the group parachor value for the group $(C)_2CHCl$ may be derived as 80.9.

Further, the mean of the observed parachor values of *tert.*-butyl chloride (Quayle, Owen and Beavers, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 3107; Vogel, *loc. cit.*) is found to be 229.4. This suggests that the group parachor value for the group $(C)_3CCl$ will be 63.3.

These values are recorded in Table I together with those for the groups $(C)CH_3$, $(C)_2CH_2$ and $(C)_3CH$.

TABLE I

Group.	[P].	Diff.	Group.	[P].	Diff.
$(C)CH_2Cl$	96.3	...	$(C)CH_3$	55.2	...
$(C)_2CHCl$	80.9	15.4	$(C)_2CH_2$	39.8	15.4
$(C)_3CCl$	63.3	17.6	$(C)_3CH$	22.2	17.6

It is seen from the results that the differences between the parachor values of successive groups show a constant increment of 2.2 in both series. The results indicate that the chlorine atom in aliphatic monochlorides appears to resemble the hydrogen

atom as regards the interference caused by these atoms. The ideal R. P. values for the groups $(C)CH_2Cl$, $(C)_2CHCl$ and $(C)_3CCl$ will be 96.3, 83.1 and 69.9 respectively.

Although Gibling has not derived value of the interference correction for $C-C-Cl$, following his method of assumption, we may derive it as follows: Since the interference correction for $C-C-C$, $C-C-N$ and $C-C-O$ are 2.2, 2.4 and 2.6 respectively, the interference correction for $C-C-F$ may be taken as 2.8. Further, the interference correction for $C-C-S$ is 2.7; hence the interference correction for $C-C-Cl$ may be assumed to be 2.9. Using this value and the group parachor value for the group $(C)CH_2Cl$ as 96.3, the group parachor values for the groups $(C)_2CHCl$ and $(C)_3CCl$ may be calculated as 78.7 and 58.9 respectively. These results, however, are not in agreement with the observed values.

The author has shown that the interference corrections for $C-C-C$, $C-C-N$ and $C-C-O$ have the same value of 2.2. Hence, it would be likely that the interference correction for $C-C-F$ and $C-C-Cl$ may also have the same value of 2.2. But the present results indicate that the interference correction for $C-C-Cl$ is zero. These results indicate the necessity of modification of the concept of interference. According to Gibling (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 299), the effective volume contribution of a given atom will depend on the nature of the atoms to which it is linked. Interference is bound to occur when atoms, though not directly united, are brought into a close conjunction. On the assumption that the smallest hydrogen atom would cause no interference,* he obtained a value of 2.2 for the interference caused by the non-linked atoms C_1 and C_2 in

It is now seen that the "relatively large" chlorine atom in

also produces no interference with C_1 . Thus, the variation of the value of the interference correction with the size of the atoms (in the grouping $C-C-X$) is not so simple as it appears from the values obtained by Gibling.

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